

Enhancing Intrusion Detection System Performance: A Comprehensive Study on Feature Selection and Machine Learning Algorithms

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Abstract: This research addresses the challenges faced by Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) in processing vast and diverse data streams generated by modern technologies. By integrating feature selection methods with various machine learning algorithms, the study aims to enhance IDS performance while reducing computational costs. Using a multi-class dataset encompassing benign and common DDoS attacks, the research employs the ANOVA feature selection technique to reduce dimensionality and preserve critical features. Empirical evaluations of various machine learning algorithms, including Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Stochastic Gradient, Adaboost, K-Nearest Neighbour, Extra Trees, and Naïve Bayes, demonstrate their effectiveness in intrusion detection. Comparative analysis is conducted using performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The results indicate that the Random Forest algorithm outperforms the others, achieving an accuracy of 91.98%. Additionally, incorporating feature selection techniques significantly enhances the performance of IDS models. The paper concludes by highlighting the importance of addressing data imbalance challenges and optimizing feature selection processes to improve IDS performance in future research.

Keyword: Intrusion Detection System (IDS), Machine Learning Techniques, Anomaly Detection

1. Introduction

Recent advancements in technologies such as cloud computing, big data, and social media are generating enormous amounts of data (Hashem et al. ,2015). Extracting valuable information from this data is highly challenging and has become essential for advertisers, analysts, and businesses. Additionally, transferring massive amounts of data across a network has become a significant issue (Provost and Fawcett, 2013). An Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is a critical safeguard designed to protect networks from attacks and malicious activities..(Efe et al. ,2022) Through the integration of other protective technologies like firewalls and access control systems, an IDS monitors network functions, analyzes data, and identifies potential threats and vulnerabilities.(Younus and Alanezi,2023) It operates by recognizing malicious traffic and attacks, ensuring the security and integrity of network resources and systems.(Pillai and Polimetla ,2024). An anomaly-based IDS detects data packets in network traffic by analyzing packets that deviate from the established normal profile. This paper applies machine learning algorithms to effectively identify intrusions. Machine learning involves data-driven techniques for managing regression and classification tasks. These methods include Support Vector Machines (SVM) for both regression and classification,

Naive Bayes for classification, and k-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) for both regression and classification.

2. Materials & Method:

2.1. Materials (Dataset Used and Dataset Description)

In this research CICDDoS2019 data set utilized which is a multi-class dataset. It contains benign and common DDoS attacks, which match the real-world data. In this dataset, there are different types of attacks like DRDOS_LDAP, DRDOS, NetBIOS, DRDOS_DNS, DRDOS_NTP, and Benign. Later attacks were carried out during this period. There are four DDoS attacks like DRDOS_LDAP, DRDOS NetBIOS NetBIOS, DRDOS_DNS, DRDOS_NTP on the training day and testing day. Now, this dataset has 400000 rows and 88 columns and it has target column that is label column. The number of objective of labels is given below in the table format.

Table 1. Number of object of each label in the data set

Serial Number	Type of Label	Number of Object
1	Benign	14849
2	DRDOS_LDAP	99970
3	DRDOS_NetBIOS	99425
4	DRDOS_DNS	98290
5	DRDOS_NTP	87466

2.2. Method

2.2.1. Data Preprocessing:

Data pre-processing is a crucial step in preparing raw data for machine learning models. In this research also applied data pre-processing with the mentioned data set. Steps are given below:

- Handle the missing value. This process done by deleting rows with missing data and imputing missing values using techniques like mean, median, mode.
- Identifying and removing duplicate entries to ensure each data point is distinct
- Detecting and correcting inaccuracies in the dataset, such as outliers or misreported values.
- Converting non-numerical labels into numerical values. This process done using label encoding to make categorical data understandable for machine learning algorithms.
- Adjusting the range of data features. Scaling ensures features are on a similar scale, often using Standardization (z-score normalization).
- Rows with missing or infinite values and columns that do not contribute to the predictive model are dropped.

2.2.2 Feature Selection

Feature selection is crucial in machine learning for reducing data dimensionality by selecting the most significant features. This process helps improve model accuracy by removing irrelevant and redundant features, thereby reducing overfitting and underfitting. In this research paper, ANOVA feature selection used to select the best features as show in fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Feature selection

2.2.3 Machine Learning Model:

Machine learning empowers computers to learn from data, boosting performance on future tasks (Alpaydm, 2010). Various machine learning methods are utilized to forecast attacks within Test datasets, which serve as the system's training data. These algorithms play a crucial role in accurately predicting and categorizing attacks for optimal efficiency.

2.2.3(a) Decision Tree:

This is utilized for forecasting discrete-valued target functions, wherein the acquired function is symbolized by a decision tree (Mitchell, 1997). Key elements including the root node, edges, and leaf nodes constitute the fundamental components of a decision tree structure. Furthermore, these learned trees can be transformed into sets of if-then rules, thereby improving their interpretability for human users (Quinlan, 1986). These learning methodologies are widely recognized as prominent inductive inference algorithms and have showcased their efficacy in diverse domains, ranging from medical diagnosis (Aha et al., 1991) to assessing the credit risk of loan applicants (Hand & Henley, 1997).

2.2.3(b) Random Forest:

The primary issue encountered with the decision tree algorithm is its tendency to overfit the training data, leading to overfitting (Breiman, 2001). This challenge has prompted the extensive adoption of ensemble learning methods such as Random Forests. In a Random Forest, numerous decision trees are trained, each receiving a bootstrapped sample of observations (Breiman, 2001). This process involves creating a random sample of

observations with replacement, maintaining the original number of observations. Additionally, at each node, only a subset of features is considered when identifying the optimal split.

2.2.3(c) Logistic Regression:

Logistic regression stands out as a widely-used supervised learning classification algorithm, primarily utilized to forecast the probability of a target variable. It represents one of the quicker machine learning algorithms suitable for various classification tasks, such as predicting diabetes or detecting spam emails (James et al., 2013).

The logistic regression model generates instances for at least two classes, constructed based on probabilities derived from a logistic function applied to each class within the dataset. This logistic function stems from linear regression, wherein each data point carries a certain probability represented by a linear function (Hosmer Jr et al., 2013).

2.2.3(d) Stochastic Gradient Classifier

The Stochastic Gradient Classifier, also known as Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), is a straightforward yet effective optimization algorithm widely used in machine learning (Ruder, 2016). It efficiently determines the values of parameters or coefficients for functions, aiming to minimize a given cost function. This optimization process allows SGD to find the model parameters that best fit the predicted outputs with the actual data, making it a valuable tool in various machine learning applications.

2.2.3(e) Adaboost Classifier

The AdaBoost Classifier, short for Adaptive Boosting, is an ensemble learning method that combines multiple weak learners to create a strong classifier (Freund & Schapire, 1996). In AdaBoost, each weak learner focuses on the mistakes made by the previous learners, thus improving overall accuracy. This technique has been widely used in various machine learning applications due to its ability to handle complex data and improve predictive performance.

2.2.3(f) The Extra Trees Classifier

Extra Trees Classifier (Extremely Randomized Trees) is a composite method building on random forests. It creates a forest of trees using random splits of all data, reducing overfitting for better generalization. (Geurts, Ernst, & Wehenkel, 2006). The classifier averages the predictions from all trees, providing robust and accurate classification results.

2.2.3(g) Naïve Bayes

It is an application of Bayes' Theorem, introduced by Bayesian probability theory, which assumes all events are independent.

Multinomial Naïve Bayes

The Multinomial Naïve Bayes (NB) algorithm operates similarly to Gaussian NB but assumes that features follow a multinomial distribution. This classifier is commonly used for discrete data and is rarely applied to continuous data. For text classification, this algorithm is often used with the bag of words model (Rish, 2001).

Gaussian Naïve Bayes

Gaussian Naïve Bayes is widely used and can handle both discrete and continuous data. This algorithm consider that the continuous information movement a Gaussian (normal) distribution (Murphy, 2012).

2.2.3(h) k-Nearest Neighbour (KNN)

KNN Classifier is one of the oldest and most fundamental supervised classifiers. It classifies data based on the principle of the closest data point, where the value of k determines the number of nearest neighbours to consider for classification. The class of a given data point is predicted based on the distance to, and the consistency with, its closest neighbours (Altman, 1992). This method assumes that similar points are located near each other in the feature space.

2.2.4 Performance Metrics

The classifiers mentioned in section 2.2.3 will be evaluated based on the following performance metrics

2.2.4(a) Accuracy: Equation (1) represents the accuracy which gives the predictive performance of the model. By accuracy the total percent of detected and wrong alarms formed by an IDS model can be measured. It shows the total rate of success of any IDS and is computed as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{T_P + T_N}{T_P + T_N + F_P + F_N} \quad (1)$$

Where T_P = true positive, T_N = true negative, F_P = false positive, F_N = false negative

2.2.4(b) Precision: Sometimes the false negative rate (FNR) called as precision. It is the proportion of miscategorized attacks to the total number of attacks which are occurred. The precision is given below at equation (2). It indicates the number of exact positive forecasts which are predicted.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{T_P}{T_P + F_P} \quad (2)$$

Where T_P = true positive, F_P = false positive.

2.2.4(c) Recall: Another performance metric is recall which is shown in equation (3). By Recall how many of the actual positives were recalled can be measured. It has also significance as important metric, as having positives which are not detected, or false negatives, might have important results in some areas.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{T_P}{T_P + F_N} \quad (3)$$

Where T_P = true positive, F_N = false negative

2.2.4 (d) F-Score: The F1-Score provides further information about the IDS’s performance. It is critical since it considers false positives and negatives. Sometimes the distribution of labels is unequal or unbalanced, and then the f1-scores is convenient in particular. The F-Score, which can be predicted using Equation (4), exhibits the consistency of recall and sensitivity.

$$F\text{-Score} = 2x \frac{p \times R}{p + R} \tag{4}$$

Where R = Recall, P = Precision

3. Results and Discussion

The classification algorithms mentioned in section 2.2.3 has been trained with dataset mentioned in section 2.1. The confusion matrix and other performance metrics is given below:

Fig 2. Confusion Matrix of the classification Model (a) using Decision Tree algorithm (b) using Random Forest algorithm (c). using Logistic Regression algorithm (d) using Stochastic Gradient Classifier (e) using Adaboost algorithm (f). using the Extra Trees Classifier algorithm (g). Using multinomial Naïve Bayes (h).Using Gaussian Naïve Bayes (i)KNN algorithm

The test datasets are used to evaluate the built models. Performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score are used to present the results and for comparative analysis of the classifiers. Table 2 represents the performance of the algorithms.

Table 2. Performance metrics of classification algorithms

Algorithm Name	Accuracy	Precision			Recall			F1- Score		
		weighted	micro	macro	weighted	micro	macro	Weighted	micro	macro
Decision Tree (DT)	90.45	90.43	90.44	92.17	90.44	90.44	92.17	90.44	90.44	92.17
Random Forest (RF)	91.98	92.48	91.98	93.87	91.98	91.98	93.39	91.91	91.98	93.36
Logistic Regression (LR)	71.25	67.7	71.25	70.91	71.25	71.25	74.17	64.35	71.25	68.29
Stochastic Gradient(SG)	71.28	73.1	71.28	74.41	71.28	71.28	74.33	62.69	71.28	66.45
Adaboost Classifier(AC)	65.59	62.36	65.59	68.17	65.59	65.59	71.37	58.4	65.59	65.28
Extra tree classifier(ETC)	91.47	91.48	91.47	93.03	91.47	91.47	93.02	91.44	91.47	93.01
Gaussian naïve bayes(GNB)	58.97	62.5	58.97	66.17	58.97	58.97	62.69	53.07	58.97	57.76
Multimomial naïve bayes(MNB)	69.7	66.25	69.7	66.84	69.7	69.7	68.52	61.57	69.7	62.34
K-NN	80.69	79.99	80.69	83.2	80.69	80.69	83.93	79.99	80.69	83.27

Fig 3. Performance comparison of various classification algorithm (a) based on accuracy (b) based on weighted precision (c) based on weighted F1-score

Form table 2 and figure 3 it is evident that Random Forest (RF) demonstrates the highest accuracy at 91.98%, with balanced precision, recall, and F1-scores, making it the best performer overall. Extra Tree Classifier (ETC) closely follows, showing high accuracy (91.47%) and strong metrics across all categories. Decision Tree (DT) exhibits robust performance with 90.45% accuracy and consistent precision, recall, and F1-scores, slightly below RF and ETC. K-Nearest Neighbours (K-NN) provides good performance with 80.69% accuracy and high macro-averaged scores, indicating effectiveness across different classes. Logistic Regression (LR) and Stochastic Gradient (SG) show moderate accuracy around 71%, with LR displaying slightly better recall and SG having higher precision. Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB) achieves moderate performance with 69.7% accuracy, better suited for discrete data like text classification. AdaBoost Classifier (AC) has lower performance with 65.59% accuracy but shows higher recall for minority classes. Gaussian Naïve Bayes (GNB) exhibits the lowest accuracy at 58.97%, indicating issues with effectively handling both false positives and false negatives.

4. Conclusion

This work explores the impact of feature selection on Intrusion Detection System (IDS) model performance. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is utilized for feature selection, with various machine learning algorithms (K-Nearest Neighbours, Decision Trees, Logistic Regression, Random Forests, Stochastic Gradient Classifiers, and Adaboost) evaluated on the CIC-DDOS 2019 dataset. The findings reveal that ANOVA-based feature selection significantly improves attack classification across all evaluated metrics (accuracy, recall, precision, F1-score). The Random Forest classifier achieves the highest accuracy among the tested algorithms. Future research directions include optimizing the feature selection process and addressing the challenge of unbalanced data distribution within IDS datasets.

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